

SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART VI. MANGANESE MONO-ACETATO COMPLEX

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The composition of the complex formed between Mn^{2+} and acetate ions has been found to be $(MnAc)^+$, from a study of the equilibrium H^+ -ion concentrations in mixtures of equimolar manganese chloride and acetic acid solutions, by 'Job's method of continued variation', using a new index property, viz., the increase of hydrogen-ion concentration.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium, $MnAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Mn^{2+} + Ac^-$, has been found to $6c.3 \times 10^{-3}$ at $28.3 - 30.0^\circ$, by the direct application of "law of mass action", taking into account the activity coefficients of individual ions, calculated from the ionic strength of the solution mixture of manganese chloride and acetic acid solutions, employing the "Debye-Hückel limiting law".

The procedure described in Part I (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 269) of this series for lead acetato complex was applied here for the determination of the thermodynamic dissociation constant 'K' for the equilibrium, $(MnAc)^+ \rightleftharpoons Mn^{2+} + Ac^-$ (where Ac^- represents acetate ion).

$$K = \frac{a_{Mn^{2+}} + a_{Ac^-}}{a_{(MnAc)^+}} = \frac{c_{Mn^{2+}} c_{Ac^-}}{c_{(MnAc)^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{Mn^{2+}} f_{Ac^-}}{f_{(MnAc)^+}}$$

In the present case the p_H values for solution mixtures, containing a volume '1-x' of manganese chloride and 'x' of acetic acid, 'x' varying between 0.1 and 0.9 with both parent solutions at concentration, 'C', were determined. The composition of the complex formed has been found out, as in the case of lead acetato complex (*loc. cit.*) by the application of "Job's method of continued variation" using the increase (Y) of the hydrogen-ion concentration in the mixture over the total hydrogen-ion concentrations of the parent solutions at the same dilution, as the index property. From the Y/x plots it has been observed that the maximum value of 'Y' corresponds to the reacting proportion 1:1 for manganese chloride and acetic acid. This shows that under the present experimental conditions, the following equilibrium alone is most predominant, and the formation of higher complexes, e.g. $MnAc_2$, $MnAc_3^-$ etc., is negligible. The reaction can therefore be written as, $Mn^{2+} + HAC \rightleftharpoons (MnAc)^+ + Ac^-$, assuming complete dissociation of manganese chloride and hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Manganese chloride and acetic acid used were of Analar variety. All solutions of manganese chloride and acetic acid were prepared in conductivity water and in stock solutions manganese was determined as sulphate, and the acid by titration with a standard alkali solution. These were used to prepare solutions of desired concentration 'C'. After keeping the mixtures, as shown in Table I, in a closed room for 3 hours, the p_H values were determined by following an identical procedure and observing same precautions as adopted in Part II (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 279).

TABLE I
[HAc stands for acetic acid]

I-x.	Solution mixtures studied.			Concentrations of parent solutions.			
	HAc.	MnCl ₂ .	Water.	p_H .	$(Y \times 10^4)$.	p_H .	Increase in $[H^+]$: $(Y \times 10^4)$.
0.1	(i) 9 c.c.	1 c.c.	...	2.727	1.35	2.453	16.62
	(ii) 9	...	1 c.c.	2.764		2.73	
	(iii) ...	1	9	4.74		...	
0.2	(i) 8	2	...	2.702	3.54	2.418	20.41
	(ii) 8	...	2	2.790		2.75	
	(iii) ...	2	8	4.98		...	
0.3	(i) 7	3	...	2.699	4.75	2.401	22.93
	(ii) 7	...	3	2.819		2.775	
	(iii) ...	3	7	5.11		...	
0.4	(i) 6	4	...	2.709	5.57	2.395	24.42
	(ii) 6	...	4	2.857		2.80	
	(iii) ...	4	6	5.15		...	
0.5	(i) 5	5	...	2.727	5.94	2.401	25.17
	(ii) 5	...	5	2.895		2.837	
	(iii) ...	5	5	5.13		...	
0.6	(i) 4	6	...	2.757	6.13	2.421	24.75
	(ii) 4	...	6	2.947		2.88	
	(iii) ...	6	4	5.13		...	
0.7	(i) 3	7	...	2.805	5.83	2.451	23.54
	(ii) 3	...	7	3.01		2.926	
	(iii) ...	7	3	5.14		...	
0.8	(i) 2	8	...	2.877	5.07	2.508	20.93
	(ii) 2	...	8	3.09		2.996	
	(iii) ...	8	2	5.15		...	
0.9	(i) 1	9	...	3.01	4.33	2.623	15.39
	(ii) 1	...	9	3.27		3.10	
	(iii) ...	9	1	5.16		...	

* It is found from experiments with $C = 0.2$, that amount of H^+ ions liberated, when manganese chloride is dissolved in water, is negligible as compared to those in solutions (i) and (ii) and also to the value of Y . Therefore at $C = 0.5$, it is neglected.

TABLE II

The symbol used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part I (loc. cit.).

I-x.	Solution mixtures.		Conc. of parent solutions ($M/5$). Conc. of parent solu. (M/a).			
	HAc.	MnCl ₂ .	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.
0.1	9	1	0.0614	46.69	0.1509	12.95
0.2	8	2	0.1208	17.54	0.2998	6.54
0.3	7	3	0.1804	11.86	0.4498	3.76
0.4	6	4	0.2402	8.98	0.5985	2.32
0.5	5	5	0.2999	6.91	0.7482	1.50
0.6	4	6	0.3598	5.47	0.8980	1.01
0.7	3	7	0.4197	4.45	1.048	0.67*
0.8	2	8	0.4797	3.55	1.198	0.44*
0.9	1	9	0.5397	2.71	1.348	0.28*

* These could not be shown in Fig. 2.

N. B. Ionisation const. of HAc at 28.3-30° was taken to be $K_a = 1.75 \times 10^{-5}$ (Hurned and Owen, loc. cit.).

FIG. 1

strength ' μ ', the reason being the inapplicability of the "Debye-Hückel limiting law" to solutions of finite ionic strengths. This curve, however, has not been used to determine

FIG. 2

the value of ' K ' by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. The plot $pK (= -\log K)$ against ' $\sqrt{\mu}$ ' gives a straight line curve as represented in Fig. 2, which when extrapolated to ' $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$ ' gives the value of pK corresponding to the thermodynamic constant ' K '. These values of pK and ' K ' at ' $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$ ' are 1.22 and 60.3×10^{-3} at 28.3–30° respectively.

The authors' best thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Bhattacharyya for offering facilities.